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An expression screen reveals induction of Ephrin A2 in non-small cell lung cancer.

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Axonal guidance factors are important during neurodevelopment for establishment of CNS circuitry through the use of attractive and repulsive cues (1, 2). We hypothesize activation of axonal guidance factors is a signature transcriptional feature of the solid tumor transcriptome in humans, that guidance factors promote metastasis and invasive behavior, and that their increased expression in the solid tumor confers inferior patient survival outcome. We describe here differential expression and transcriptional induction of Ephrin A2 (3-5) in non-small cell lung cancer, the leading cause of death from cancer in humans. Overall survival was nearly twice as long in stage T3 NSCLC patients with low tumor expression of EphA2.

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